

**Multi-layered
Security
Technologies**
for hyper-connected
smart cities

D2.5: Integration Plan

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Glossary

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application programming interface
APP	Application
D	Deliverable
DUT	Device under test
EU	European Union
ID	Identifier
IoT	Internet of Things
IRL	Integration Readiness Level
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
OS	Operating System
P2P	Peer-to-peer
SDK	Software Development Kit
SRA	System Readiness Assesment
SRL	System Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
T&R	Trust and Reputation
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package
Y	Year

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the document

This deliverable is the outcome of Task 2.3 “Overall Integration”, which focuses on the overall plan to integrate components and modules developed and deployed in WP4. It also generates the integrated system providing the M-Sec functionalities as they have been specified in WP3.

In order to integrate all the components and modules, an integration plan has been devised. The integration plan consists of a methodology together with a series of best practices, workplans and testing schemes.

For clarity, the integration points between assets are being presented by Use Case, as each Use Case has its own interaction with the assets.

In Section 3, all subsections include:

- A short description of the Use Case.
- An interaction matrix with all the integration points between the assets used in the UC.
- An interaction diagram showing the integration points in a functional view.
- A subsection to identify the type of each interaction.
- A timeframe to integrate and prioritize assets in order to complete the integration of all assets into the Use Case in a timely manner.

1.2 Relationship to other work packages and tasks

Deliverable D2.5 Integration Plan uses as input the M-Sec requirements and architecture introduced in WP3 as well as the developments performed in the WP4. As a result, the following deliverables are taken into account:

- Deliverable D3.1 about M-Sec requirements from Task 3.1
- Deliverable D3.3 about M-Sec architecture from Task 3.2.
- Deliverable D4.1 about IoT Security from Task 4.1.
- Deliverable D4.3 about cloud and data level security from Task 4.2.
- Deliverable D4.5 about P2P level security and blockchains from Task 4.3.
- Deliverable D4.7 about application level security from Task 4.4.
- Deliverable D4.9 about end-to-end security from Task 4.5.

The results of this deliverable will be used as input for Task 2.4, which will validate and evaluate the procedures described in this document.

2. Overall methodology followed

A comprehensive understanding of the project’s development status (system readiness) can aid more informed system-level technical and managerial decisions throughout the life cycle of the project. Towards this direction, a **System Readiness Assessment (SRA)** process provides visibility over the course of the development life cycle into the entire system. The SRA measures the readiness of all system components, focuses on the readiness of integration between components internal to the system and is performed at multiple times over the course of the system life cycle.

After the study of several SRAs, one of the most completed ones was chosen¹ and slightly adapted to the needs of the M-Sec project, in order to make it possible to keep track of the M-Sec system and subsystems maturity in a methodical and quantitative manner. The next subsections introduce the several metrics being used for that purpose, as well as the relation between them and the general SRA process planned to be followed.

2.1 Metrics

This section describes the five metrics used throughout the SRA process. Two of these metrics, the **Technology Readiness Level (TRL)** and **Integration Readiness Level (IRL)**, are assigned. The three remaining **System Readiness Metrics (Component SRL, Composite SRL, and SRL)** are computed. Sample calculations for determining specific metrics are provided in subsection 2.2.

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

The TRL is a systematic metric/measurement to assess the maturity of a particular technology (component) and to allow consistent comparison of maturity between different types of technologies (components). TRL values range from 1 to 9. The TRL was initially pioneered by J.C. Mankins² at the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Goddard Space Flight Center in the 1980s as a method to assess the readiness and risk of space technology.

Table 1: Technology Readiness Level Definition/Description.

TRL	Definition/Description
9	Actual System Proven Through Successful Mission Operations
8	Actual System Completed and Qualified Through Test and Demonstration
7	System Prototype Demonstration in Relevant Environment
6	System/Subsystem Model or Prototype Demonstration in Relevant Environment
5	Component and/or Breadboard Validation in Relevant Environment
4	Component and/or Breadboard Validation in Laboratory Environment
3	Analytical and Experimental Critical Function and/or Characteristic Proof-of-Concept

¹ Austin, Marc & York, Donald. (2015). System Readiness Assessment (SRA) an Illustrative Example. *Procedia Computer Science*. 44. 486-496. 10.1016/j.procs.2015.03.031.

² Mankins, J.C., *Technology Readiness Levels*, NASA, 1995.

2	Technology Concept and/or Application Formulated
1	Basic Principles Observed and Reported

Integration Readiness Level (IRL)

The IRL is a metric to measure the integration maturity between two or more components. Integration Readiness Levels, in conjunction with TRLs, form the basis for the development of the System Readiness Level (SRL). The IRL values range from 0 to 9. IRLs represent the systematic analysis of the interactions between various components and provide a consistent comparison of the maturity between **integration points**.

Table 2: Integration Readiness Level Definition/Description.

IRL	Definition/Description
9	Integration is Mission Proven through successful mission operations.
8	Actual integration completed and Mission Qualified through test and demonstration in the system environment.
7	The integration of technologies has been verified and validated with sufficient detail to be actionable.
6	The integrating technologies can accept, translate, and structure information for its intended application.
5	There is sufficient control between technologies necessary to establish, manage, and terminate the integration.
4	There is sufficient detail in the quality and assurance of the integration between technologies.
3	There is Compatibility (i.e., common language) between technologies to orderly and efficiently integrate and interact.
2	There is some level of specificity to characterize the interaction (i.e. ability to influence) between technologies through their interface.
1	An interface (i.e. physical connection) between technologies has been identified with sufficient detail to allow characterization of the relationship.

System Readiness Metrics

There are three system readiness metrics that are computed in the SRA process. These are the Component SRL, Composite SRL, and SRL. While the TRL provides the metric for describing component knowledge, the IRL is a metric that provides a description of architectural knowledge or how the components are integrated. System readiness provides a snapshot in time of the readiness of the entire system.

Component SRL

A Component SRL is the System Readiness Level of an individual component of the system and its integration links. Component SRLs are used to identify which system components are lagging or may be too far ahead in terms of their readiness and thus require project management actions and/or engineering attention.

Composite SRL

The Composite SRL measures the SRL of the whole system or all of the components of the system integrated together. The SRA approach calculates the Composite SRL by averaging the Component SRLs and rendering

the value in a decimal format. As with any calculation involving an average, the user needs to be aware of the potential risk of masking a Component SRL that may be significantly lagging or leading the average.

SRL

The SRL is obtained by converting the Composite SRL to a 1 to 5 integer scale, with 5 being the readiest. The conversion to an integer scale facilitates reporting and interpretation of the results, similar to the conversion of a numerical score to letter grade.

Table 3: System Readiness Level Definition/Description.

IRL	Definition/Description
5	Operations & Support
4	Production & Development
3	System Development & Demonstration
2	Technology Development
1	Concept Refinement

Figure 1: TRL, IRL, and SRL

presents in an abstract manner the relations between TRL, IRL, and SRL. TRL is a metric of the maturity of individual components (colored disks in the figure), IRL a metric of the maturity of integration points/links between components (edges between disks) and SRL a metric of the maturity of the whole system (exterior circle), taking under consideration both TRLs and IRLs.

Figure 1: TRL, IRL, and SRL

2.2 Calculations

This subsection explains in detail and demonstrates by example the calculations and matrix mathematics used in the SRA process to determine the SRL. Calculating the SRL is a function of the TRL and IRL matrices.

The TRL matrix provides a snapshot in time of the state of the system with respect to the technology readiness of its components. The TRL is defined as a vector with n components where TRL_i is the TRL of component i.

The IRL matrix represents the integration of different components with each other from a system perspective. The integration between components i and j is represented by IRL_{ij} in the IRL matrix. The theoretical integration of component i to itself is denoted by IRL_{ii} and is assumed to be a maximum, i.e. 9, in this SRA approach. Zeroes in the matrix indicate no planned integration. At a minimum, each of the components of a system is connected to one other component. This integration is bidirectional, and it is assumed that the IRL is the same in each direction; thus, the IRL matrix is symmetric.

The formation of the TRL and IRL matrices for a system with n components is shown in Equations (1) and (2).

$$[TRL]_{nx1} = \begin{bmatrix} TRL_1 \\ TRL_2 \\ \dots \\ \dots \\ TRL_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (1) \quad [IRL]_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} IRL_{11} & IRL_{12} & \dots & \dots & IRL_{1n} \\ IRL_{21} & IRL_{22} & \dots & \dots & IRL_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & IRL_{33} & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ IRL_{n1} & IRL_{n2} & IRL_{n3} & \dots & IRL_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In the matrices represented, the TRL levels correspond to values 1 through 9, while the IRL values range from 0 to 9. Before performing the matrix math, these values are normalized by dividing by 9, the highest value. For example, an IRL of 9 has a normalized value of 1 for element IRL_{ij} . Similarly, an IRL of 5 has a normalized value of 0.556.

The SRL matrix consists of one element for each of the constituent components and, from an integration perspective, quantifies the readiness level of a specific component with respect to every other component in the system while also accounting for the development state of each. In order to calculate a value of the SRL from the TRL and IRL values, an SRL matrix is generated by obtaining the product of the IRL and TRL matrices:

$$[SRL]_{nx1} = [TRL]_{nx1} \times [IRL]_{n \times n} \quad (3)$$

The corresponding SRL_i for each component i is then divided by m_i , as shown in Equation (4), to obtain its normalized value. The m_i term is the number of integrations of component i with every other component as defined by the system architecture. This includes the integration of the component with itself. Dividing by m_i also allows each component to be neutrally weighted looking at the component in isolation with its nearest neighbors, yielding well-behaved and consistent mathematical and statistical properties.

$$\text{Component } SRL_i = \frac{SRL_i}{m_i} \quad (4)$$

The Component SRLs are important, as they provide an indicator of the readiness of the individual component and its associated integrations. Examination of the individual Component SRL values relative to each other identifies those components that are lagging or may too far ahead in their “readiness.”

The Composite SRL for the system is the average of the Component SRL values, as shown in Equation (5):

$$\text{Composite } SRL = \frac{\left(\frac{SRL_1}{m_1}\right) + \left(\frac{SRL_2}{m_2}\right) + \dots + \left(\frac{SRL_n}{m_n}\right)}{n} \quad (5)$$

The Composite SRL is the average of the Component SRLs. As with any calculation involving an average, the user needs to be aware of the potential risk of masking a Component SRL that is significantly lagging or leading the average, reiterating the importance of assessing and monitoring the individual Component SRLs.

Composite SRLs are defined on a scale from 0 to 1 with a value carried out to three decimal places. Composite SRL values are translated to whole numbers consistent with TRL and IRL scaling for ease of

interpretation. To translate the 0 to 1 scale to a 1 to 5 scale (the one presented in Table 3), an SRL Translation Model is used to map the decimal values to whole number values.

Figure 2 sums up all of the above steps through an example. On the top-left, the IRL matrix of the system is given, as well as the TRL matrix of its components. On the top-right, the corresponding interaction diagram of the system is given. From the IRL and TRL tables, the Components SRLs, the Composite SRL, and the SRL (both normalized and scaled) are produced.

Figure 2: Calculation of SRL

2.3 Methodology and Future Steps

While the first half of the 2nd year focused on the development work, the second half will mainly focus on the integrations and deployments. During that time, the above metrics will be continuously monitored to avoid pitfalls that can occur when readiness is only assessed once or twice. Throughout the lifecycle of the project, M-Sec is going to present the evolution of several matrices in order to monitor the progress of the project.

In the following sections, for each Use Case, the M-Sec components being used as well as the initial integration points (interactions) between them have been identified. These interactions are presented with integration matrixes and interaction diagrams. Since the main scope of this deliverable is presenting the integration plan (and not the integration results per se), the integration matrixes only indicate the existence of interactions and not their maturity. Thus, the integration matrixes' fields have as values only 0 (no interaction between the components) and 1 (integration point identified).

Future deliverables presenting the integration results will contain:

- Components' list and their TRL progress (from Y1 to Y2 and Y3).
- IRL matrixes for each Use Case and for the whole M-Sec system and their evolution (from Y1 to Y2 and Y3).
- SRL matrixes for each Use Case and the whole M-Sec system and their evolution (from Y1 to Y2 and Y3).

3. Interaction points between assets

3.1 Use Case 1

Short description for Use Case 1 and summary of requirements

The use case will deploy a series of novel IoT devices in selected locations in the city of Santander both to retrieve interesting environmental data along with a measurement of noise levels, and to be capable of sketching crowd heat maps, using as a source of information the number of mobile phones in the area.

- Users will check measurements through a dedicated webpage / app.
- Possibility to rate the information received.
- Introduce gaming features and rewards.

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- Deployed devices should not impact the scenario negatively nor affect the daily operations as they are before their deployment.
- The service should facilitate the visualisation of real-time information in a map or in a list (physical sensing information).
- The service should facilitate the visualisation of historical information in a map or in a list (physical sensing information).
- The application should provide a tool to analyse data and extract statistics in a simple and easily understandable way for the city economic development division and event organisers.
- The local architecture should be scalable and integrated with others.

The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The mobile phone IDs of end-users interacting with the city spots where the pilot is carried out should be anonymised.
- The associated web application should protect the privacy of the end-user, propose several levels of management of personal data, and give the option of modifying the privacy parameters any time.

Interactions matrix

All interactions points that are expected to take place between all the assets of the Use Case 1 can be seen in the Table 4 interaction matrix. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in Section 2), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 4: Interactions matrix of Use Case 1

	Park guide	TST IoT crowd-counting devices	TST IoT environmental devices	Companion Database	Node-RED	KEIO SOXFire	Quorum Blockchain framework	IoT Marketplace/ Blockchain middleware	T&R Model engine/tool	Modal Transition System Analyser	Secured components for devices and gateways	YNU Honeypot (IoT POT)
Park Guide												
TST IoT crowd-counting devices			1			1	1			1		
TST IoT environmental devices			1			1	1			1		
Companion Database						1	1					
Node-RED					1		1		1			
KEIO SOXFire												
Quorum Blockchain framework												
IoT Marketplace/ Blockchain middleware									1			
T&R Model engine/tool												
Modal Transition System Analyser												
Secured components for devices and gateways												1
YNU Honeypot (IoT POT)												

Interaction diagram

The expected interactions in this use case will focus on the ones happening among the IoT devices designed by TST to keep track of environmental measurements and provide a figure related to the number of people gathering in selected spots. The analysis of potential attacks to these devices will be carried out through the IoT POT provided by YNU, as depicted in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Interaction diagram of Use Case 1

In addition, there are several other project assets that may have an impact on this scenario, since they could cover more interesting areas related to this use case goals.

Identification of interactions for Use Case 1

The interaction points detected in the Use Case 1:

Table 5. Identification of interactions Use Case 1

From	To	Type of integration point
Secured components for devices and gateways	TST IoT crowd-counting devices	Hardware installation
Secured components for devices and gateways	TST IoT environmental devices	Hardware installation
TST IoT crowd-counting devices	Companion DB	Use of an API
TST IoT environmental devices	Companion DB	Use of an API
TST IoT crowd-counting devices	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
TST IoT environmental devices	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
TST IoT crowd-counting devices	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API
TST IoT environmental devices	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API
IoT Marketplace	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
IoT Marketplace	Companion DB	Use of an API
Companion DB	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
Park Guide	Companion DB	Use of an API
Node-RED	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
Node-RED	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API
Node-RED	Modal Transition System Analyser	To be determined
T&R Model engine/tool	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API
YNU Honeypot (IoTPOT)	Secured components for devices and gateways	To be determined

Timeframe for integration

Table 6 shows the planning for the main integrations in Use Case 1. This planning has been made taking into account the specific needs of every asset in the Use Case. As expected, there are assets that are considered more critical than others because of their functionality for the use case or of the type of integration.

The other integrations might be covered by other use cases or into the integration of one of the main integrations.

Table 6. Timeframe for main asset integration in Use Case 1

Asset	Initial month	End month
TSmartT platform & TST IoT devices	M18	M21
Secured components for devices and gateways	M18	M21
Honeypot (IoT POT)	M19	M21
Blockchain framework	M27	M29

3.2 Use Case 2

Short description for Use Case 2 and summary of requirements

Use Case 2, “Home monitoring & Wellbeing Tele-assistance for active and independent aging people”, is based in the Worldline’s asset, Connected Care, a solution designed to improve quality of life of elderly people by offering services based on monitoring their home activity and helping them to live independently at home while offering security and peace of mind to their families.

With Connected Care, users are monitored and looked after using home sensor devices such as a smart plug, bed occupancy sensor, window/door open sensor, and motion sensor. All data generated by these sensors are collected and analysed on an ongoing basis by teleoperators of the tele-assistance company in charge of taking immediate action if necessary.

The main value added and the objective of the use case and its associated pilot is to ensure through the M-Sec platform a trusted environment concerning all the sensitive data collected by these devices and privacy protection.

Therefore, the two main goals of the use case that will be probed during the execution of the pilot will be:

- Improvement of quality of life of elderly people who live alone and are not familiar with the use of new technologies.
- Improvement of data security and integrity through the use of M-Sec layers in the different elements that compound the service. For example, components (sensors, cloud systems) involved in the data stream dissemination need to be tamper-proof to prevent malicious attacks on devices.

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should let users collect information about their home activity (e.g. windows open sensor).
- The system should store massive information (such as temperature per second) in an efficient way, taking into account that not all data are expected to be recorded/stored forever.
- The system should store information (such as access to data) in a way that ensures this information will not be forgotten, and with mechanisms that allow third parties to verify that this information is correct and true.

The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should have an access control policy, binding the users with different profiles, each with different access privileges to data (the owner of the data, a person assigned by them to consult their data –family member or professional-, software administrator, technical support, security officer, etc.)
- The system should have several policies of access to the data, depending on the role of the user and the data the user is trying to access to. Anonymous users should be given no access to any data related to users.
- The system should have a dashboard for matching roles to policies and privileges of access.
- The system should support an easy-to-use mechanism that enables the owner of the data to grant privileges of access to other users in an understandable way.
- The system should support mechanisms for authentication and authorisation of the users, including updates of the users' proofs of access privileges.
- The system should include security measures that protect data transmitted over the network at the application level against eavesdropping (encryption and peer authentication).

Interactions matrix

In this interaction matrix, we can see all the interaction points between all the assets that we have in the use case. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in Section 2), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 7: Interactions matrix of Use Case 2

Use Case 2	Worldline Connected Care Assistance	Companion Database	Caburm Home Monitoring Devices	KEIO SOXFire	Development Method for a secure service	Node-RED	Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware	Modal Transition System Analyser	Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio	IoT Marketplace	T&R Model engine/tool
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	1								1		
Companion Database						1				1	
Caburm Home Monitoring Devices								1			
KEIO SOXFire					1			1			
Development Method for a secure service					1						
Node-RED						1	1				
Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware										1	
Modal Transition System Analyser											
Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio											
IoT Marketplace											1
T&R Model engine/tool											

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram shows how each asset interacts with the others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 4: Interaction diagram of Use Case 2

Identification of interactions for Use Case 2

The interaction points detected in the Use Case 2:

Table 8. Identification of interactions Use Case 2

From	To	Type of integration point
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	Companion DB	Use of an API
Worldline Connected Care Assistance	Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio	Framework assistance
Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio	Caburm Home Monitoring Devices	Framework assistance
KEIO SOXFire	Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio	Framework assistance
IoT Marketplace	Companion DB	Use of an API
Companion DB	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
Node-RED	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
Modal Transition System Analyser	Node-RED	To be determined
Development Method for a secure service	Node-RED	To be determined
Node-RED	Modal Transition System Analyser	To be determined
T&R Model engine/tool	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API

Timeframe for integration

Table 9 shows the planning for the main integrations in Use Case 1. This planning has been made taking into account the specific needs of every asset in the Use Case. As expected, there are assets that are considered more critical than others because of its functionality for the use case or the type of integration.

The other integrations might be covered by other use cases or into the integration of one of the main integrations.

Table 9. Timeframe for main asset integration in Use Case 2

Asset	Initial month	End month
Companion DB	M18	M23
Quorum Blockchain	M18	M23
Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio	M22	M26

3.3 Use Case 3

Short description for Use Case 3 and summary of requirements

This use case provides a client application that allows urban environment monitoring entities (for example, local governments) to visualise spatially and temporarily dense environmental data. Using the application, the entities are enabled to serve their citizens with sophisticated environment monitoring better. In this scenario, an automotive sensing platform is used to generate real-time environmental sensor data streams from all over the city of Fujisawa, leveraging a hundred mobile sensing trucks.

This use case illustrates how the M-Sec platform secures such a mobile sensing platform by meeting the following objectives. Firstly, the heterogeneous components involved in the data stream dissemination are secured so that they are not cracked by malicious attackers. Secondly, the data streams are secured so that the data do not tamper in the network between their source and destination. Finally, the data streams do not harm citizens' privacy. Thus an automated privacy protection mechanism should be provided.

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should collect environment sensor data.
- The system should be able to handle a large number of data streams concurrently.
- The system should be able to transfer the data streams in real-time.
- The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:
- The system needs to secure the heterogeneous components involved in the data stream dissemination, so that they are not cracked by malicious attackers.
- The system needs to secure the data streams so that the data do not tamper in the network between their source and destination.
- The system should protect the data streams from malicious attackers at the edge and distributed cloud platform.
- The system should disseminate the environment data stream to citizens securely.
- The system should not harm citizens' privacy; thus, an automated privacy protection mechanism should be provided.
- The system should grant access only to those with valid access rights.

Interactions matrix

In Table 10 interaction matrix we can see all the interaction points between the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 3. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in Section 2), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 10: Interactions matrix of Use Case 3

	IoT Marketplace	Companion Database	IoT Intrusion Detection & Protection System	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	KEIO SOXFire	Monitoring & Visualisation Tool	Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware	Secured components for devices and gateways	Security Management Tool	T&R Model engine/tool	YNU Honeypot
IoT Marketplace				1				1	1		
Companion Database				1		1					
IoT Intrusion Detection & Protection System				1	1						1
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform				1	1		1				
KEIO SOXFire											1
Monitoring & Visualisation Tool											
Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware											
Secured components for devices and gateways											
Security Management Tool											
T&R Model engine/tool											
YNU Honeypot											

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 5: Interaction diagram of Use Case 3

Identification of interactions for Use Case 3

The interaction points detected in the Use Case 3:

Table 11. Identification of interactions Use Case 3

From	To	Type of integration point
Companion DB	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
KEIO SOXFire	Companion DB	Use of an API
IoT Marketplace	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
Security Management Tool	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API
T&R Model engine/tool	IoT Marketplace	Use of an API
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
YNU Honeypot	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Framework assistance
Secured Components for devices	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Framework assistance
IoT Intrusion Detection & Protection System	YNU Honeypot	Installation
Monitoring & Visualization Tool	IoT Intrusion Detection & Protection System	To be determined
Monitoring & Visualization Tool	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Framework assistance

Timeframe for integration

Table 12 shows the planning for the main integrations in Use Case 4. This planning has been made taking into account the specific needs of every asset in the Use Case. As expected, there are assets that are considered more critical than others because of its functionality for the use case or the type of integration.

The other integrations might be covered by other use cases or into the integration of one of the main integrations.

Table 12. Timeframe for critical asset integration in Use Case 3

Asset	Initial month	End month
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	M18	M24
KEIO SOXFire	M20	M24
Honeypot (IoT POT)	M24	M27

3.4 Use Case 4

Short description for Use Case 4 and summary of requirements

In this use case, “Hyper-connected citizen care applications” will be created for a range of different purposes and for different stakeholders. On the one hand, a government officers’ application will collect city-related data (such as urban waste generation per household, pedestrian flow or traffic flow data, etc.) through the M-Sec architecture and analyse the data to produce value-added data that affect citizens efficiently. Citizens’ applications, on the other hand, will consume that value-added data to empower their decision on related topics towards better (physical, mental or social) wellbeing or QoL.

The Scenario specific requirements for this use case are the following:

- The system should collect heterogeneous data on citizens’ life in real time.
- The system should be able to handle a large number of data streams concurrently.
- The system should be able to transfer the data stream in real time.
- The local architecture should be scalable and can be integrated with others.
- Deployed devices will not impact negatively in the scenario nor affect the daily operations as they are before their deployment.
- The associated web application should provide and visualise environment information collected over the city.
- The application should provide a tool to analyse data and extract statistics in a simple and easily understandable way for the city environment division and citizens.
- The Security/Privacy specific requirements for this use case are the following:
- The system needs to secure the heterogeneous components involved in the data stream dissemination so that they are not cracked by malicious attackers.
- The system needs to secure the data streams, so that the data are not tempered in the network between their source and destination.
- The system should not harm citizens’ privacy; thus, an automated privacy protection mechanism should be provided.
- The system should disseminate the data stream to municipalities and citizens securely
- The system should protect the data streams from malicious attackers at the edge and distributed cloud platform
- The system should grant accesses from whom own a valid access right
- The cloud system should store the data securely so that they are not disclosed to any party without permission

Interactions matrix

In Table 13 interaction matrix we can see all the interaction points between the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 4.

Table 13: Interactions matrix of Use Case 4

Use Case 4

	Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	Ganonymizer	Companion Database	IoT Marketplace	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	KEIO SOXFire	Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware	Secured components for devices and gateways	Security Management Tool	T&R Model engine/tool	UC4.1 APP (Garbage Collector)	UC4.2 APP (=SmileWave)
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	1	1		1	1							
Ganonymizer												1
Companion Database			1		1	1				1	1	
IoT Marketplace												
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform					1		1					
KEIO SOXFire										1	1	
Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware												
Secured components for devices and gateways												
Security Management Tool											1	1
T&R Model engine/tool											1	1
UC4.1 APP												
UC4.2 APP (=SmileWave)												

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 6: Interaction diagram of Use Case 4

Identification of interactions for Use Case 4

The interaction points detected in the Use Case 4:

Table 14. Identification of interactions Use Case 4

From	To	Type of integration point
Deep Counter	Ganonymizer	Use of an API
Deep Counter	Companion DB	Use of an API
Deep Counter	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Framework assistance
Deep Counter	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
SmileWave	Ganonymizer	Use of an API
IoT Marketplace	Companion DB	Use of an API
Garbage Collector	Companion DB	Use of an API
KEIO SOXFire	Companion DB	Use of an API
SmileWave	Companion DB	Use of an API
Companion DB	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API

KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Secured components for devices	To be determined
Gargabe Collector	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
SmileWave	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
Gargabe Collector	Security Management Tool	To be determined
SmileWave	Security Management Tool	To be determined
Gargabe Collector	T&R Model engine/tool	To be determined
SmileWave	T&R Model engine/tool	To be determined
Honeypot (IoTPOt)	Secured components for devices	Installation in the server side
Honeypot (IoTPOt)	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Installation in the server side

Timeframe for integration

Table 15 shows the planning for the main integrations in Use Case 4. This planning has been made taking into account the specific needs of every asset in the Use Case. As expected, there are assets that are considered more critical than others because of its functionality for the use case or the type of integration.

The other integrations might be covered by other use cases or into the integration of one of the main integrations.

Table 15. Timeframe for critical asset integration in Use Case 4

Asset	Initial month	End month
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	M18	M24
KEIO SOXFire	M20	M24
Honeypot (IoTPOt)	M24	M27
Secured components for devices and gateways	M24	M27

3.5 Use Case 5

Short description for Use Case 5 and summary of requirements

This use case focuses on creating a marketplace to distribute data while ensuring confidentiality, integrity, availability, and privacy of data following GDPR/PIPA regulations so that people or organizations in EU and Japan can utilize the data more securely and effectively. Data to be exchanged in the marketplace are:

- Data from citizens and visitors: Purchase data, health data collected by pedometers, personal data collected by smartphones, data collected by questionnaires.
- Local government data: Statistic data, local information such as photos or reports collected by city staff
- Web data: Any data automatically collected from the internet (environmental data, etc.)
- IoT data: Data collected from IoT devices (cameras, etc.) owned by companies or local governments.

Requirements:

- The local architecture should be processed securely.
- The cloud system should store the data securely and could be accessed from EU and Japan.
- The devices should be used to collect user’s data, such as behavior characteristic data.
- The marketplace will be secured by using Blockchain technology.

Interactions matrix

Table 16: Interactions matrix of Use Case 5

Use Case 5	Companion Database	Fujisawa MinaRepo	Ganonymizer	IoT Marketplace	KEIO SOXFire	Mobile Wallet	Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware	Security Management Tool	SmileWave
Companion Database	1	1				1			
Fujisawa MinaRepo		1					1		
Ganonymizer								1	
IoT Marketplace				1					
KEIO SOXFire									
Mobile Wallet						1			
Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware									
Security Management Tool									
SmileWave -> on mobile									

Interaction diagram

The integration diagram shows how each asset interacts with others and which role takes each one versus the others.

Figure 7: Interaction diagram of Use Case 5

Identification of interactions for Use Case 5

The interaction points detected in the Use Case 5:

Table 17. Identification of interactions Use Case 5

From	To	Type of integration point
IoT Marketplace	Companion DB	Use of an API
SmileWave	Ganonymizer	Use of an API
Companion DB	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
KEIO SOXFire	Companion DB	Use of an API
Fujisawa MinaRepo	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
Security Management Tool	Fujisawa MinaRepo	Use of an API
Mobile Wallet	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API

Timeframe for integration

Table 18 shows the planning for the main integrations in Use Case 4. This planning has been made taking into account the specific needs of every asset in the Use Case. As expected, there are assets that are considered more critical than others because of its functionality for the use case or the type of integration.

The other integrations might be done by other use cases or into the integration of one of the main integrations.

Table 18. Timeframe for critical asset integration in Use Case 5

Asset	Initial month	End month
Ganonymizer	M18	M24
Mobile Wallet	M18	M24
IoT Marketplace	M18	M24

3.6 Use Case 6

Short description for Use Case 6 and summary of requirements

This use case takes into account the current knowledge and habits of citizens in both Santander and Fujisawa in order to promote a participatory environment in which they contribute to reflect the pulse of every city

- Personally reporting on various events
 - State of the public road
 - Traffic incidents

Therefore, Use Case 6 will create and implement the participatory environment in which citizens of Santander and Fujisawa provide their reports on various events while also sending quantitative measurements of physical sensing provided by sensors that incorporate their cell phones.

- Citizens will feel more involved in the daily operations of their corresponding cities.
- Municipal officers will get an additional information resource to help them carry out their jobs.

Interactions matrix

In the Table 19 interaction matrix we can see the interaction points between all the assets that are expected to take place in the different stages of Use Case 6. It should be noted that, as the assets are duplicated in Vertically/Horizontally (the matrix is a symmetric one, as described in Section 2), only the fields above the diagonal up (or only the ones below it) have to be taken care of.

Table 19: Interactions matrix of Use Case 6

	Companion Database	Fujisawa MinaRepo	Ganonymizer	IoT Marketplace	KEIO SOXFire	Mobile Wallet	Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware	Security Management Tool	SmileWave
Companion Database			1	1		1			
Fujisawa MinaRepo				1			1		
Ganonymizer								1	
IoT Marketplace					1				
KEIO SOXFire									
Mobile Wallet						1			
Quorum Blockchain framework/ Blockchain middleware									
Security Management Tool									
SmileWave -> on mobile									

Interaction diagram

The expected interaction in this use case will focus on the one happening among the applications which were originally deployed in each one of the cities involved in M-Sec, and that will act as the foundation of the application, which will be developed in Use Case 6.

Figure 8: Interaction diagram of Use Case 6

Identification of interactions for Use Case 6

The interaction points detected in the Use Case 6:

Table 20. Identification of interactions Use Case 6

From	To	Type of integration point
IoT Marketplace	Companion DB	Use of an API
SmileWave	Ganonymizer	Use of an API
Companion DB	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API
KEIO SOXFire	Companion DB	Use of an API
Fujisawa MinaRepo	KEIO SOXFire	Use of an API
Security Management Tool	Fujisawa MinaRepo	Use of an API
Mobile Wallet	Quorum Blockchain	Use of an API

Timeframe for integration

Table 21 shows the planning for the main integrations in Use Case 4. This planning has been made taking into account the specific needs of every asset in the Use Case. As expected, there are assets that are considered more critical than others because of its functionality for the use case or the type of integration.

The other integrations might be done by other use cases or into the integration of one of the main integrations.

Table 21. Timeframe for critical asset integration in Use Case 6

Asset	Initial month	End month
SmileWave	M18	M21
KEIO SOXFire	M18	M21
Fujisawa MinaRepo	M18	M21

3.7 Overall system-level interaction points view

Interaction diagram

The expected interaction in this diagram will focus on all the assets involved in M-Sec.

Figure 9: Interaction diagram of M-Sec

Interactions matrix

In the Table 22 interaction matrix, we can see the interaction points between all the assets that are expected to take place in M-Sec.

Table 22. Overall interaction matrix

M-Sec

	Park guide	TST IoT crowd-counting devices	TST IoT environmental devices	Companion Database	Node-RED	KEIO SOXFire	Quorum Blockchain framework	IoT Marketplace/ Blockchain middleware	T&R Model engine/tool	Modal Transition System Analyser	Secured components for devices and gateways	YNU Honeypot (IoTPOt)	Worldline Connected Care Assistance	Caburm Home Monitoring Devices	Development Method for a secure service	Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio	Security Management Tool	IoT Intrusion Detection & Protection System	KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform	Monitoring & Visualisation Tool	Fujisawa MinaRepo	Ganonymizer	Mobile Wallet	SmileWave	Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)	Garbage Collector
Park Guide	1					1																				
TST IoT crowd-counting devices		1				1	1			1																
TST IoT environmental devices			1			1	1			1																
Companion Database				1	1	1						1											1	1	1	
Node-RED				1	1	1		1					1										1	1	1	
KEIO SOXFire											1			1				1		1				1	1	
Quorum Blockchain framework							1															1				
IoT Marketplace/ Blockchain middleware								1								1						1				
T&R Model engine/tool									1														1		1	
Modal Transition System Analyser																										
Secured components for devices and gateways											1															
YNU Honeypot (IoTPOt)																										
Worldline Connected Care Assistance													1													
Caburm Home Monitoring Devices														1												
Development Method for a secure service																										
Eclipse sensiNact platform and Studio																										
Security Management Tool																										
IoT Intrusion Detection & Protection System																										
KEIO Mobile Sensing Platform																										
Monitoring & Visualisation Tool																										
Fujisawa MinaRepo																										
Ganonymizer																										
Mobile Wallet																										
SmileWave -> on mobile																										
Deep Counter (Garbage Identification AI)																										
Garbage Collector																										

4. Integration types

During the process of development of assets and although some of them are not finished yet, some types of integration points have been detected or pointed out because of their characteristics.

The following list shows a set of integration points that may fit the integration of the assets with some others that may be used once developments end.

- Use of an API.
- Installation in the server side.
- Integration in-code.
- Use of an SDK.
- Framework.
- Hardware installation.

The descriptions types of integration points are:

- **Use of an API:** An application programming interface (API) is a set of subroutine definitions, protocols, and tools for building application software, intended to simplify the implementation and the maintenance of this software. In general terms, it is a set of clearly defined methods of communication between various software components.
- **Installation in the server side:** Installation requires that the Operating System (OS) supports the installation, so it is OS dependant. It allows then the interaction with this tool/asset by an API, exchange of files or direct communication by other means.
- **Integration in-code:** The in-code integration can be a set of functions or methods that can be used in the code. It does not provide as many tools and abstraction as a framework and is not as wide and generic as an SDK. It could be considered a “little framework” or a “little SDK”.
- **Use of an SDK:** A software development kit (SDK) is a collection of software development tools in one installable package. They ease the creation of applications by having a compiler, debugger, and perhaps a software framework. They are normally specific to a hardware platform and operating system combination. So, here has to be taken into account the type of hardware and also the language used to develop the application.
- **Framework assistance:** A framework is an abstraction in which software providing generic functionality can be selectively changed by additional user-written code, thus providing application-specific software. It provides a standard way to build and deploy applications, and it is a universal, reusable software environment that provides particular functionality as part of a larger software platform to facilitate the development of software applications, products, and solutions. Frameworks may include support programs, compilers, code libraries, toolsets, and application programming interfaces (APIs) that bring together all the different components to enable the development of a project or system.
- **Hardware installation:** The hardware installation is the modification of a hardware device by installing physically other components that will modify its behaviour.

4.1 Testing Plan per Type of integration point

Integration points will be repeated across all Use Cases. This subsection will provide an explanation of how these interactions will be tested, depending on their type.

The integration testing will be performed by the owner of each Use Case per integration point. This will take place manually at first by using mockup objects or test scenarios. For the execution of integration testing, it is important to have clear instructions from the module providers with steps to reproduce in order to test the service successfully.

Use of an API

An API is essentially a contract between the client and the server or between two applications. Before any implementation test can begin, it is important to make sure that the contract is correct. That can be done first by inspecting the spec (or the service contract itself, for example, a Swagger interface or OpenAPI reference) and making sure that endpoints are correctly named, that resources and their types correctly reflect the object model, that there is no missing functionality or duplicate functionality, and that relationships between resources are reflected in the API correctly.

API test actions

Each test is comprised of test actions. These are the individual actions a test needs to take per API test flow. For each API request, the test would need to take the following actions:

1. **Verify correct HTTP status code.** For example, creating a resource should return 201 CREATED, and unpermitted requests should return 403 FORBIDDEN.
2. **Verify response payload.** Check valid body and correct field names, types, and values — including in error responses.
3. **Verify response headers.** HTTP server headers have implications on both security and performance.
4. **Verify basic performance sanity.** If an operation was completed successfully but took an unreasonable amount of time, the test fails.

Test flows

1. **Testing requests in isolation.** Executing a single API request and checking the response accordingly. Such basic tests are the minimal building blocks we should start with, and there is no reason to continue testing if these tests fail.
2. **Multi-step workflow with several requests.** Testing a series of requests which are common user actions, since some requests can rely on other ones. For example, we execute a POST request that creates a resource and returns an auto-generated identifier in its response. We then use this identifier to check if this resource is present in the list of elements received by a GET request. Then we use a PATCH endpoint to update new data, and we again invoke a GET request to validate the new data. Finally, we DELETE that resource and use GET again to verify it no longer exists.

Installation in the server side

Each tool/asset is different. Although the tool/asset requires an installation, it does not mean that it might be exposing an API, SDK, or framework. If it exposes an API, SD or it is a framework, its section should be read. Otherwise, follow the described generic tests.

For the communication between two components there are two principles that if they are not met, there is no communication.

- There is an input.
- There is an output.

Assuming these two statements, some test actions can be performed.

Generic test actions

Each test is comprised of test actions. These are the individual actions a test needs to take per test flow. For each call, the test would need to take the following actions:

1. **Verify correct response.** The information returned is what is expected according to the documentation.
2. **Verify correct response in case of error.** The code/error returned has sufficient information in order to deal with it.
3. **Verify basic performance sanity.** If an operation was completed successfully but took an unreasonable amount of time, the test fails.

Test flows

1. **Testing requests in isolation.** Executing a single call and checking the response accordingly. Such basic tests are the minimal building blocks we should start with, and there's no reason to continue testing if these tests fail.
2. **Multi-step workflow with several calls.** Testing a series of calls which are common user actions, since some calls can rely on other ones.

Integration in-code

This type of integration requires the called Unit Testing. Unit Testing is a level of software testing where individual units or components of a software are tested. The purpose is to validate that each unit of the software performs as designed. A unit is the smallest "testable" part of any software. It usually has one or a few inputs and usually a single output.

Usually, after the Unit Testing comes the Integration Testing, but in this particular case, as the integration is performed at a level that it would be part of the main component, it is enough with this.

Use of an SDK

An SDK usually takes the form of application programming interfaces (APIs) in the form of on-device libraries of reusable functions used to interface to a particular programming language. So the testing it is similar to the API. Following in detail:

SDK test actions

Each test is comprised of test actions. These are the individual actions a test needs to take per SDK test flow. For each SDK call, the test would need to take the following actions:

1. **Verify correct response.** The information returned is what is expected according to the documentation.
2. **Verify correct response in case of error.** The code/error returned has sufficient information in order to deal with it.
3. **Verify basic performance sanity.** If an operation was completed successfully but took an unreasonable amount of time, the test fails.

Test flows

1. **Testing requests in isolation.** Executing a single SDK method and checking the response accordingly. Such basic tests are the minimal building blocks we should start with, and there's no reason to continue testing if these tests fail.
2. **Multi-step workflow with several method calls.** Testing a series of methods which are common user actions since some calls can rely on other ones.

Framework assistance

As explained, a framework provides a set of tools to help and guide into a development and sometimes providing a set of utilities. The way to perform a testing plan will depend on the result of the application that makes use of it.

It can result in as follows:

- **Integration in-code**, when the framework helps with some internal calculations.
- **Integration with an API**, when the framework helps with the communication to an external API.
- **Integration with an SDK** when the framework eases the use of an SDK, providing some functionalities commonly used.

Hardware installation³

In order to perform a hardware installation testing the following sections in your test plan have to be considered:

1. **DUT Overview** – this explains what the product does at a high level, how it's used in operation and its key functions.

³ <https://www.viewpointusa.com/TM/ar/hardware-test-plan-for-complex-or-mission-critical-products/>

2. **Test equipment system diagram** – this provides a basic block diagram overview of the main hardware components of the test equipment or automated test system.
3. **Test overview** – a description of each test. How the test is performed, the stimulus involved, how results are calculated, test limits, test time goals, the intent of the test, the equipment involved, etc. See the section below for more detail.
4. **Test fixture needs** – describe how the fixture interfaces to the DUT and how the operator interacts with it (physically, so how they connect cables and whatnot, not things like software user prompts).
5. **Equipment List** – this is a list of all the equipment needed to perform the tests during manufacturing.
6. **Capacity analysis** – analyzes and provides estimates for the amount of product that can leave the factory over a period of time (takt time) from a testing standpoint.

Test Overview details

The following should be described for each test:

1. **Test intent** – Explain why the test is being conducted. It should describe at a high level what aspects will be tested. For a manufacturing test, the testing of the unit should be scoped to making sure it was built correctly and adheres to critical design specifications. It should not be a design validation test.
2. **Test limits** – List the limits for pass/fail
3. **Test time & takt time goals** – these are estimates at this point, based on a combination of historical data and bottom-up analysis.
4. **Test equipment needs** – a type of equipment and any unique capabilities

5. Conclusions

At this stage, the plan to accomplish the first version of M-Sec is covered. The main integration points have been stated, and by now, some of them are already at a good level of integration. At the end of the integration, it is expected that several modules/components/assets will interact successfully with each other in an integrated environment. In the next period, focus will be given on fully integrating all core assets and cover all business requirements of the project. Moreover, focus on testing and ensuring a stable and efficient system to be offered to end-users will be one of the main priorities.